

The Social and Psychological Behaviors of Adolescents of Social Media Users

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ABSTRACT

Social media, a virtual form of interaction, having the qualities of real, connects the users for sharing and broadcasting the views in online. As the media is a tool, its success mostly depends upon how the users use pictures and messages which are interesting to them. Today the social media mostly useful to the adolescents for creating awareness on political and cultural issues, world happenings, giving chance to expand social relationship, making social confidence, heightening literacy, using to get social support from online friends, helping to develop their motor skills and co-ordination, etc. The negative influence of the social media is influencing violence where adolescents unable to distinguish the reality and fantasy, lead to irresponsible sexual behavior, fall prey to the idea of commercialization of happiness, diverting the mind from concentrating from their study, etc. This study mainly concentrates on how the social media affects the social and psychological behaviors of adolescents especially the users who are having different social and cultural backgrounds. The data for the study is collected from the social media network adolescents users especially from Tamilnadu, India along with the reference materials connected to the study.

SOCIAL MEDIA AS INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP

Social media is one of the parts of our social life. It influences the Adolescents in all aspects of their lives. Adolescents generally use the social media for listening and watching videos, pictures, messages, movies, TV shows, games, etc. Through the social media one can get the experience of great excitement, frustration and tension. It requires more

emotional involvement, cognitive effort and brain activation. Some familiar social media forms are Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, MySpace and SnapChat. Through the social media one can pursue interpersonal relationships with friends and family members. Social media some ways influence the attitudes and behaviors of Adolescents in almost all the walks of their life including political, personal and consuming aspects of life.

The social media personally influences the Adolescents in their way of life regarding their day today activities especially their appearance, relationship, travelling, habits, fitness activities, customs, knowledge, etc. The data for the study is collected from the 200 Adolescents of social media users from Tamilnadu, India between the age groups 12 to 24 irrespective of their gender, education, status, profession, region, etc.

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ADOLESCENTS

The study reveals the Adolescents use the social media (Chau, 2010) in five aspects viz., 1. Social media should not have many restrictions 2. Through social media one can easily share the information with others 3. One can easily get an informal support to their activities 4. Easily understand the views of others and 5. It is an alternative way of socializing function.

1. LEARNING THE SUBJECTS

Social media is an avenue for the Adolescents for learning the subjects. It makes the learners to be creative interactive in learning (Chau, 2010). The Adolescents use the social media for the conventional learning methods (Clarke Person, O’Keeffe, 2011). The Adolescents of the study use the social media for sharing their opinions with their fellow learners in the subjects like art, music, and games, and also for improving and exchanging the knowledge through discussing the concerned subjects and topics.

2. CONNECTING THE PEOPLE

In the study, the Adolescents use the social media to connect with the family and friends for sharing photos, messages, videos etc. It is used to contact with far distance

people through internet. The Adolescents used the social media to buy products through the sites staying at homes and used to do some works and getting for some useful information.

PSYCHOLOGICAL, PHYSICAL AND SOCIOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF ADOLESCENTS

The Adolescent users of social media of Tamilnadu facing various psychological, physical and sociological problems (Gross, 2004) like 1. sleep deprivation, 2. excessive fatigue, 3. decreased immune system, 4. lack of proper exercise, 5. poor personal hygiene, 6. eye strain, 7. social isolation, 8. lack of real life social relationship, 9. familial relationship problems, and 10. increasing family conflict.

The chart shows what kind of psychological, physical and sociological problems faced by the Adolescents of Tamilnadu by the social media

Table-1

Sl.No.	Level of Adolescents	Number of user of various level of Adolescents	Percentage
1.	Sleep deprivation	18	9%
2	Excessive fatigue	21	10.5%
3	Decreased immune system	16	8%
4	Lack of proper exercise	23	11.5%
5	Poor personal hygiene	18	9%
6	Eye strain	19	8%
7	Social isolation	22	11%
8	Lack of real life social relationship	20	10%
9	Familial relationship problems	17	8.5%
10	Increasing family conflict	26	13%
Total		200	100%

The social media create some other problems among the Adolescents are 1. decline in study habits 2. cyber bullying, 3. sexual predators, and 4. exposing to pornographic materials. These problems lead the Adolescents to social desirability bias and quality-of-life issues along with high level protest behavior.

Chart-1

BEHAVIORAL FACTORS INFLUENCE THE ADOLESCENTS

The behavioral factors influence the Adolescents of social net working sites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Google+, Pinterest are shyness, moody behavior, loneliness and stressed feeling. These factors affects the contents that dominate its ‘feeds’ which determent the behavior of its users.

The study shows the social media influences the personal, political and consumer behavior of Adolescents in many aspects like privacy issues, opinions on politicians, buying habits etc.

POLITICAL ATTITUDES OF ADOLESCENTS

The Political ramifications of Adolescents are algorithms; attention bias and negative comments on perceive messages. The negative comments reduce the persuasive influence of the articles and positive comments are not strengthening the effect of persuasive values.

The online negative exposure makes uncivil comments that lead to hostile cognitions. Every influence depends upon the attitudes of Adolescents whether it is positive or negative aspects.

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF SOCIAL NETWORKING

The human behavior related to social networking such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn assist the Adolescents users for creating and maintaining their relationship and influenced the individual differences of extraversion and introversion. The extraversion reflects the dominant attitudes of the adolescents. The introversion refers to the disposition of shyness and social phobia. The most important psychological factors that influence the Adolescents are 1.depression 2. anxiety 3. attachment and 4. self identity.

1. DEPRESSION

Depression mainly based on the relationship of the individual activities which leads to the symptoms of psychopathology and bias.

2. ANXIETY

The anxious Adolescents behave more actively on social media sites. It is a positive relationship of social networking usage and depression.

3. ATTACHMENT

It is connected with interpersonal relationship. The attachment is recognized with four styles of Adolescents viz. i) secure, ii) anxious preoccupied, iii) dismissive avoidant and iv) fearful avoidant (Benjamins and Colleagues, 2015).

4. SELF IDENTITY

Social media explore and form the self identity of Adolescents through self exploration, compensation and social facilitation. Self exploration describes the investigation of reacts of others. Social compensation describes how to overcome the shyness and social facilitation helps to facilitate relationship formation.

5. BELONGINGNESS

It is the personal experience of Adolescents where the feeling being valued and fitted into the group. The Adolescent users of social media updated the daily events of their personal lives and the information which interest to them. The perception of Adolescents closed without actually have to speak with them. Each Adolescent contributes to the social media by 'liking', posts commenting, updating statuses, tweeting, posting videos and more.

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA

The social media mostly helps the Adolescents for creating awareness on cultural and political issues, world happenings, giving chance to expand social relationship, making social confidence, heightening literacy, using to get social support from online friends, helping to develop their motor skills and co-ordination with along blog and chat which help them to improve their reading and writing skills.

The most of the negative influence of the social media are violence where adolescents unable to distinguish the reality and fantasy, leads to irresponsible sexual behavior, fall prey to the idea of commercialization of happiness, diverting the mind from concentrating their study etc.

FACEBOOK

The study shows the social and psychological impact of Facebook on Adolescents can be categorized into –

- help to meet the member of family, friends and acquaintances of the Adolescents met in their real life.

- interact with the members create more trusting, close relationship
- help the users politically engaged and active
- make negative self perception and sense of self worth
- help for good business
- look like a real world
- help to promote easily of others
- create counter negative of self perception.

TWITTER

The Adolescents use the Twitter for narcissism, self validation and neurologically offers ‘intermittent rewards’ through the right type of followers, share content and informational content.

PINTEREST

Pinterest Board represents the ideal self of Adolescents. The expensive things and images of Pinterest represent desired identity. The artist and creative designer share ideal self image what the followers want.

CONCLUSION

Interactions something through social media is devoid of emotions. The Adolescents hide emotions behind social media but these platforms help them to project any image they want or want to be. Through the social media Adolescents contact their friends and acquaintances for chatting and expressing opinions on personally relevant issues. The success of social media tools depends upon how one use and depends upon the media.

In contrast the day today interactions with others are mostly a continuously process of nonverbal communication like facial expressions, tone of voice, gestures, body language,

eye contact and having physical distance between the speaker and listener. These wordless signals help to understand the true meaning of the conversation or the intensions or the cognitive and emotional effort of the speakers.

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